

Technical Bulletin for GROQ-seq Transcription Factor Function Assay

A technical bulletin on the onboarding of a transcription factor function assay to the GROQ-seq platform.

- Provides technical overview of the assay produced in our original transcription factor function proposal¹.
- Uses a gene circuit to tie transcription factor binding to bacterial cell growth.
- Produces quantitative functional measurements across approximately a 300-fold dynamic range.
- Measured over 100,000 LacI, RamR, and VanR variants across multiple experimental conditions, resulting in ~270,000 unique barcoded measurements.

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Overview

The goal of this project was to develop a pooled, quantitative assay for measuring the function of ligand-inducible transcription factors (TFs) using the Growth-Based Quantitative Sequencing (GROQ-seq) platform². Transcription factors play a crucial role in scientific research and medicine due to their importance in synthetic biology^{3,4}, their widespread and conserved structural features^{5,6}, and their clinical relevance, particularly in the study of antimicrobial resistance^{7,8}.

The assay described in this technical bulletin works by linking transcription factor function (i.e., binding to a cognate DNA operator) to cellular fitness. This is achieved using a plasmid where TF-operator binding modulates the expression of dihydrofolate reductase (DHFR). DHFR expression confers resistance to trimethoprim (TMP); therefore, changes in TF function are translated into changes in TMP resistance, which can be measured as differences in cellular growth (fitness) across four timepoints. Plasmids containing TF variants are uniquely barcoded, enabling pooled sequencing-based measurement of relative fitness. Importantly, a barcoded ladder of calibration variants is included in every pool, allowing relative fitness measurements to be converted into quantitative functional values and ensuring reproducibility across experimental batches.

The initial dataset generated by the GROQ-seq TF assay can be accessed at data.alignbio.org. The initial dataset generated quantitative TF function data for three genes of interest (GOIs): LacI, RamR, and VanR. This data release includes data for three types of libraries for each TF: site-saturation variant libraries (SSVL), error-prone PCR (epPCR) libraries, and three-position site saturation (SS) libraries (see the Dataset Description section for additional details). The long-term objective of generating these datasets is to enable the development of predictive models that can infer the effects of mutations on TF-DNA binding affinity and inducibility directly from protein sequence.

The final assay described in this technical report currently supports both variants and their operator sequences for LacI, VanR, and RamR TFs. In the future, this assay could also be readily extended to evaluate additional TFs or to systematically explore the impact of assay conditions, including antibiotic concentration, ligand identity, and other environmental factors.

Assay Details

Assay Characteristics

- This assay can produce quantitative functional measurements across approximately a 300-fold dynamic range.
- Independent barcode measurements of the same sequence produce highly consistent functional estimates, demonstrating strong biological reproducibility (across all transcription factors the mean Root Mean Square Deviation [RMSD] ≈ 0.53 and mean Spearman ≈ 0.63)⁹.
- Site-to-site reproducibility, i.e., experiments performed at two facilities using a shared protocol but with differing levels of automation and system integration, produced strong agreement between measurements (mean RMSD ≈ 0.41 and mean Spearman ≈ 0.73)⁹.

Protocols

Prior to integration into the GROQ-seq, barcode-variant associations are established for each plasmid in the TF variant library using long-read nanopore sequencing. Variant libraries are then introduced into the GROQ-seq TF experimental pipeline (Fig. 1), which consists of three main phases*:

1. TF Pooled Growth-Based Assay
2. DNA extraction¹⁰
3. TF BarSeq Preparation and Pooling

**For an in-depth description of each phase, including protocols, required reagents, consumables, and hardware, see the respective files in the Supplemental Materials for reference.*

After these three phases are complete, the pooled samples are sent for Illumina sequencing, and resulting sequencing reads are analyzed using our computational pipeline. To access the complete computational pipeline for analyzing these experiments go to:

<https://github.com/Align-to-Innovate/groqseq-pipeline>

Figure 1: A high-level overview of the GROQ-seq TF experimental pipeline.

Measurement Strain

Each TF is expressed from a circuit-bearing plasmid transformed into *E. coli* MG1655 Δ lac¹¹. A lac operon knockout strain was necessary to test the LacI transcription factor library without background expression from the host. This strain is available upon request from the Living Measurements System Foundry (LMSF) team at the National Institutes of Standards and Technology (contact: david.ross@nist.gov).

Circuit Design

The GROQ-seq TF assay employs a gene circuit connecting TF function to growth using an antibiotic resistance gene as a selection marker (Fig. 2). A promoter containing an operator sequence for each TF regulates expression of *E. coli* dihydrofolate reductase (ecDHFR), which confers trimethoprim (TMP) resistance. TF variants that bind to the operator repress ecDHFR transcription, thereby increasing sensitivity to TMP and resulting in slower growth. Small-molecule ligands were used to allosterically modulate TF-operator binding, enabling the use of the TFs as biosensors. Each circuit component was selected during circuit tuning to cover a wide dynamic range and high resolution across all calibration variant activities. Genbank files for the base library plasmids of each TF (Table 1), using what was defined as the wild-type (WT) for each TF, can be found in Supplemental Materials.

Figure 2: The GROQ-seq TF assay's plasmid diagram illustrating the barcode region, expression cassette, selection cassette, and plasmid backbone components.

Expression Cassette

The expression cassette controls expression of the Gene of Interest (GOI), in this case, the TF. The expression cassette contains a constitutive promoter, a self-cleaving ribozyme, a bicistronic design (BCD) element to stabilize translation across the TF library, and the TF variant (see base library plasmids in Supp. Materials). BCD strengths were independently chosen for LacI, RamR, and VanR to 0.75k au, 2.3k au, and 1.5k au during the circuit design process to ensure maximum dynamic range and measurement resolution for each TF calibration ladder.

Selection Cassette

The selection cassette controls expression of the selection marker, in this case, the ecDHFR. The selection cassette contains the TF cognate promoter-operator, a self-cleaving ribozyme, a BCD, and the ecDHFR gene (see base library plasmids in Supp. Materials). The selection cassette is oriented divergently (i.e., in an opposing orientation) to the expression cassette to insulate against transcriptional readthrough.

Barcode Region

This plasmid utilizes a dual barcode system to create a vast diversity of barcodes, enabling unique identification of each protein variant, often with multiple barcodes per variant. The system consists of two barcode halves separated by a homology region, where each of the barcode halves takes the form NNNWSNNNWSNNNWSNNNWSNNNWSNNNWSNNN. For additional information about the barcoding strategy please refer to the GROQ-seq Platform Proposal (section 4.2.1: Barcode Region)².

Backbone

The backbone used for variant libraries in this work is pTwist Kan Medium Copy from Twist Biosciences (South San Francisco, CA). This backbone contains a p15A origin of replication and a kanamycin resistance marker.

Plasmids

Base Library Plasmids

Genbank files for the base library plasmids for LacI, RamR, and VanR (Table 1) are included in the Supplemental Materials. The plasmids include annotations for circuit components as well as the parts used in Golden Gate cloning.

Calibration and Normalization Plasmids

Both calibration and normalization variant controls were used in this assay (Table 1), and their GenBank files can be found in the Supplemental Materials. These control variants enable the conversion of sequencing-based fitness into quantitative functional values (for more details see the GROQ-seq platform proposal², section 8: Data Analysis and Machine Learning Evaluation). All calibration and normalization variants were incorporated across all GOI libraries.

During development of the assay, mScarlet-I3¹² was used in place of the ecDHFR gene to characterize the quantitative function of each calibration variant. Refer to pLacI-WT-O1_mScar plasmid map (Table 1) in the Supplemental Materials as an example of the mScarlet calibration variants.

Table 1: GROQ-seq TF assay plasmids.

Name	Variant Description
pLacI-WT_BasePlasmid	LacI Base Library Plasmid
pRamR-WT_BasePlasmid	RamR Base Library Plasmid
pVanR-WT_BasePlasmid	VanR Base Library Plasmid
pLacI-WT-O1_ecDHFR	LacI Calibration Variant 1
pLacI-WT-O2_ecDHFR	LacI Calibration Variant 2
pLacI-WT(V52A)_ecDHFR	LacI Calibration Variant 3
pLacI-WT(V52Q)_ecDHFR	LacI Calibration Variant 4
pLacI-157(S70R)_ecDHFR	LacI Calibration Variant 5
pLacI-WT(D88N)-Oid_ecDHFR	LacI Calibration Variant 6
pLacI-WT(V80L/S279T)_ecDHFR	LacI Calibration Variant 7
pLacI-002(S69T/V80L)-Oid_ecDHFR	LacI Calibration Variant 8
pRamR-WT_ecDHFR	RamR Calibration Variant 1
pRamR-S_v8_2.3k_ecDHFR	RamR Calibration Variant 2
pRamR-S2-3-(S7F)_ecDHFR	RamR Calibration Variant 3

Name	Variant Description
pRamR-S2-3-(D9H)_ecDHFR	RamR Calibration Variant 4
pRamR-D2-1-(R103G)_ecDHFR	RamR Calibration Variant 5
pRamR-D2-1-(L98I)_ecDHFR	RamR Calibration Variant 6
pRamR-D2-1-(M141T)_ecDHFR	RamR Calibration Variant 7
pRamR-7753_ecDHFR	RamR Calibration Variant 8
pRamR-WT-v2_ecDHFR	RamR Calibration Variant 9
pVanR-WT_ecDHFR	VanR Calibration Variant 1
pVanR-am_ecDHFR	VanR Calibration Variant 2
pVanR-am_t2a_ecDHFR	VanR Calibration Variant 3
pVanR-am_alt_ecDHFR	VanR Calibration Variant 4
pLacI-norm-02	Normalization Variant 1
pRamR-norm-02	Normalization Variant 2
pLacI-WT-O1_mScar	LacI Function Variant

Experimental Design

Selection Marker

This assay is challenged by trimethoprim (TMP) at the following concentrations:

- 0 µg/mL
- 0.3 ug/mL
- 3 ug/mL
- 6 ug/mL

Ligands

This assay uses ligands at the following concentrations for each TF GOI:

- LacI: 2000 µmol/L isopropyl β-d-1-thiogalactopyranoside (IPTG)
- RamR: 250 µmol/L (S)-1-Phenyl-1,2,3,4-tetrahydroisoquinoline (IS-TIQ)
- VanR: 100 µmol/L Vanillic Acid (Van)

Plate map

All three TF libraries were assayed simultaneously in a single 96-well plate format. For each library, four TMP concentrations were tested in both the presence and absence (+/-) of the corresponding cognate ligand, with each condition represented by four replicate wells. The resulting plate map for all antibiotic and ligand conditions is shown below (Fig. 3).

Figure 3: The GROQ-seq TF assay plate map.

Dataset Description

The initial dataset collected by GROQ-seq TF assay is publicly accessible through our data portal (data.alignbio.org), enabling direct access, reuse, and integration with other protein function datasets. This dataset was collected at the Living Measurements Systems Foundry (LMSF) at the National Institute of Standards and Technology.

Variant Library Overview & Synthesis

With the plasmid circuit used for this dataset, there was a slight toxicity effect associated with high transcriptional output from the promoter-operator complex for each transcription factor.

- This resulted in a biased pattern of variant drop-out from the libraries: transcription factor variants with a high basal transcriptional output (i.e., weak binding to the cognate operator) are more likely to be missing from the dataset.
- The toxicity effect is strongest for VanR and weakest for RamR.
- We are debugging this toxicity effect and expect to release future datasets where this biased drop-out effect has been reduced or eliminated.

This data release includes data for three different types of libraries for each transcription factor:

- Site-Saturation Variant Library (SSVL): libraries consisting of variants with all possible single-amino-acid substitutions, insertions, and deletions. SSVLs were purchased from Twist Bioscience (South San Francisco, California). Quality control reports are available for all three of the SSVL libraries and can be found in the Supplemental Materials.
 - Lacl is missing sites at 158 and 162.
 - RamR is missing sites at 44–46, 177–180.
 - VanR is missing sites at 233–234.
 - Overall, the datasets cover 75%, 91%, and 66% of the possible single amino acid substitutions for Lacl, RamR, and VanR, respectively (ignoring stop codon substitutions).
- Error-prone PCR (epPCR): libraries generated using epPCR amplification of the transcription factor coding sequence, with mean non-synonymous mutations per coding sequence of 2.3, 1.9, and 1.5, for Lacl, RamR, and VanR, respectively. The epPCR libraries were purchased from GenScript USA Inc. (Piscataway, NJ).
- Three-position site saturation (SS): libraries consisting of combinations of all possible amino acid substitutions at three positions, which were chosen based on available structural information because residues at those positions are expected to contact the DNA operator. The SS libraries were produced in-house at the LMSF and included combinatorial amino acid mutations focused on three residues involved in transcription factor–DNA interactions.
 - For Lacl the three positions are: Y17, Q18, and R22
 - For RamR the three positions are: E42, G43, and R47
 - For VanR the three positions are: E33, R44, and M45

Cloning & Transformation

Protein variant libraries and random barcodes were cloned into the GROQ-seq TF backbone plasmid using a 6-part Golden Gate assembly. For the SSVL and epPCR libraries this process was performed by Clutch Biotechnologies (Burlingame, California). The parts designed for Golden Gate assembly can be found as annotations in each of the TF base plasmids with the category labeled 'Clutch'. Cloning for the SSM libraries was performed in-house at the LMSF using Gibson assembly.

All libraries were first cloned in NEB® 10-beta Competent *E. coli* (c3019-DH10B) from New England Biolabs (Ipswich, MA), then transformed into NEB® 5-alpha Competent *E. coli* DH5Alpha (c2987-5Alpha) from New England Biolabs (Ipswich, MA) for growth and maintenance, and finally into MG1655Δlac¹¹ (LMSF) before being run through the GROQ-seq platform.

Barcode Mapping

In order to map variant sequences to their unique barcodes, long-read sequencing was performed on all variant libraries. Long-read sequencing was performed by Plasmidsaurus (South San Francisco, CA).

Sequencing

For all samples coming out of the GROQ-seq TF assay, enrichment of each variant was determined by sequencing the number of barcodes present via short-read sequencing. Samples were sent to Novogene (Sacramento, CA) for barcode sequencing. All samples were sequenced with a 10B-read Illumina Novaseq flow cell followed by a second, 25B-read flow cell, yielding a total of 19.9B reads.

Data Analysis

To access the complete computational pipeline used to analyze these experiments go to: <https://github.com/Align-to-Innovate/groqseq-pipeline>. For additional specific information about data analysis and cleaning for each TF dataset, please refer to the README's attached as supplemental downloads for each library at <https://data.alignbio.org>.

The final numbers of unique variants represented in the dataset for each TF are as follows:

- LacI: 44,914
- RamR: 32,593
- VanR: 23,966

Barcode Quality Sieve

Sequential quality filters were applied to barcodes from all three transcription factor libraries. Filters were applied to the full dataset prior to TF assignment (steps 1–2) and per-TF thereafter (steps 3–9). % Retained is cumulative relative to each TF's initial barcode count.

Table 2. Barcode quality sieve

Filter		LacI			RamR			VanR		
Step		Remaining	Removed	% Retained	Remaining	Removed	% Retained	Remaining	Removed	% Retained
Start	Initial barcode dataset All barcodes from Bartender clustering with at least 200 total reads	438,119	–	100.0%	473,296	–	100.0%	369,541	–	100.0%
1	Exclude reference sequence spike-ins Spike-in controls with known sequences are retained separately for fitness calibration	438,096	23	100.0%	473,273	23	100.0%	369,518	23	100.0%
2	High-confidence protein sequence required Each barcode must have a reliable consensus CDS from Nanopore long reads: ≥60% of reads agree on one sequence, or multi-sequence alignment quality ≥30 at every base	105,940	332,160	24.2%	92,292	380,981	19.5%	115,263	254,255	31.2%
3	Plasmid length matches expected size Modal Nanopore read length must be within 0.1% of the expected plasmid size. Removes barcodes with insertions or deletions in the backbone	98,306	7,634	22.4%	86,149	6,143	18.2%	104,003	11,260	28.1%

Filter	LacI			RamR			VanR		
Step	Remaining	Removed	% Retained	Remaining	Removed	% Retained	Remaining	Removed	% Retained
<p>4</p> <p>Regulatory action site detected in reads The promoter/operator region must be detected in enough Nanopore reads to be statistically consistent with it being present on the plasmid, barcodes where the site is detected far less often than expected are assumed to be missing it (see note a)</p>	96,523	1,783	22.0%	84,413	1,736	17.8%	101,475	2,528	27.5%
<p>5</p> <p>Action site sequence is correct When the action site is sequenced with high confidence, it must exactly match the expected sequence with zero mismatches (ambiguous bases ignored)</p>	95,821	702	21.9%	84,246	144	17.8%	100,253	1,222	27.1%
<p>6</p> <p>All backbone elements present For barcodes with ≥ 10 Nanopore reads, every backbone element must have at least one supporting read (KanR antibiotic resistance, p15a origin of replication, ecDHFR selection marker)</p>	95,804	17	21.9%	84,239	7	17.8%	100,223	30	27.1%
<p>7</p> <p>Backbone element sequences are correct When the ecDHFR selection marker and its regulatory region are sequenced with high confidence, they must exactly match the expected reference sequence</p>	93,978	1,826	21.5%	81,938	2,301	17.3%	97,673	2,550	26.4%

Filter	LacI			RamR			VanR		
Step	Remaining	Removed	% Retained	Remaining	Removed	% Retained	Remaining	Removed	% Retained
8 Operator assigned to correct transcription factor The operator sequence must be recognised and assigned to the expected TF library. Barcodes with operators from a different TF, or that cannot be assigned, are excluded	93,813	165	21.4%	81,286	652	17.2%	94,602	3,071	25.6%
9 Operator sequence matches a known variant The operator must perfectly match one of the expected natural operator variants, or be flagged as low-confidence, confirmed operator mutations are excluded	93,793	20	21.4%	81,193	93	17.2%	94,154	448	25.5%
Final Clean dataset	93,793	344,326	21.4%	81,193	392,103	17.2%	94,154	275,387	25.5%

Overall retention (steps 1–9): LacI: 93,793 / 438,119 barcodes retained (21.4%) RamR: 81,193 / 473,296 barcodes retained (17.2%) VanR: 94,154 / 369,541 barcodes retained (25.5%)

Filter definitions. (a) Action site detection threshold. Each Nanopore read independently covers the action site with probability p ; on an intact plasmid $p \approx 0.5$ (roughly half of reads are long enough to reach the site). The count of reads containing the site therefore follows Binomial($n, 0.5$), with expected value $\mu = 0.5n$ and standard deviation $\sigma = 0.5\sqrt{n}$. A barcode is retained if $\text{action_seq_count} > 0.5n - \sqrt{0.5n}$. Substituting μ , the threshold equals $\mu - \sqrt{\mu}$, which is exactly $\sqrt{2} \approx 1.41$ standard deviations below the expected count regardless of n (verified: $z = -\sqrt{\mu} / \sigma = -\sqrt{0.5n} / (0.5\sqrt{n}) = -\sqrt{2}$ for all n). Under a normal approximation this corresponds to a one-sided p -value of $\approx 7.9\%$: a barcode is excluded only if there is less than a 7.9% probability of observing so few action site reads by chance, given that the site is present. Because the threshold is a fixed number of standard deviations below the mean rather than a fixed fraction, the minimum required fraction varies with read depth, rising from $\sim 15\%$ at $n = 4$ to $\sim 48\%$ at $n = 1,000$ and approaching 50% asymptotically. Plasmid length: modal read length must be less than $1.001\times$ the expected plasmid size (LacI 4,653 bp; RamR 4,164 bp; VanR 4,298 bp). Action site: the promoter/operator region targeted by the TF; required in $\geq 50\%$ of reads (threshold = $0.5 \times n - \sqrt{0.5 \times n}$ reads, where n is total Nanopore read count per barcode). Backbone elements: KanR (antibiotic resistance), p15a (origin of replication), ecDHFR (selection marker), each must be detected in at least one read for barcodes with ≥ 10 total Nanopore reads. Sequence correctness: evaluated only for barcodes where the element is sequenced with high confidence (i.e., consensus quality ≥ 30 at all positions); low-confidence barcodes are retained. Operator mutations: a value of 0 indicates a perfect match to a known operator variant; -1 indicates low-confidence assignment (retained); ≥ 1 indicates confirmed mismatches (excluded). CDS confidence: high confidence requires either $\geq 60\%$ of Nanopore reads agreeing on a single sequence, or multi-sequence alignment quality ≥ 30 at every position with $\geq 60\%$ per-base agreement

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